

STUDY OF THE ACID COMPOSITION OF RAPESES SQUEEZE GROWED IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article discusses the issues of studying the fatty acid and acid composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The fatty acid composition of rapeseed squeeze is rich in unsaturated and monounsaturated fatty acids, which are not synthesized in the body and come with food. The acid composition of rapeseed squeeze was also studied, which indicates that it contains valuable water- and fat-soluble acids. The article provides a comparative analysis of the fatty acid and acid composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarusian selection.*

Keywords: rapeseed squeeze, acid, composition, fatty acid, polyunsaturated fatty acids, monounsaturated fatty acids, biological value, erucic acid, tocopherol, choline, oleic acid.

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida yetishtiriladigan raps siqmasining yog' kislotalari tarkibini o'rganish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Raps siqmasining yog' kislotalari tarkibi to'yinmagan va mono to'yinmagan yog'li kislotalarga boy bo'lib, ular organizmda sintez qilinmaydi va oziq-ovqat bilan ta'minlanadi. Raps siqmasining kislotali tarkibi ham o'rganildi, bu uning tarkibida suvda va yog'da eriydigan qimmatli kislotalarning mavjudligini ko'rsatadi. Maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasi va Belarus seleksiyasida yetishtirilgan raps siqmasining yog' kislotalari tarkibining qiyosiy tahlili keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: raps siqmasi, kislota tarkibi, yog' kislotalari, ko'p to'yinmagan yog'li kislotalar, bir to'yinmagan yog'li kislotalar, biologik qiymati, eruk kislotalari, tokoferol, xolin, oleyin kislotalari.

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются вопросы изучения жирнокислотного и кислотного состава выжимок рапсовых семян, выращенных в Республике Узбекистан. Состав жирных кислот рапсового жмыха богат ненасыщенными и мононенасыщенными жирными кислотами, которые не синтезируются в организме и поступают с пищей. Также был изучен кислотный состав рапсового жмыха, который свидетельствует о наличии в нем ценных водо и жирорастворимых кислот. В статье приведен сравнительный анализ жирнокислотного и кислотного состава рапсового жмыха, выращенного в Республике Узбекистан и Белорусской селекции.*

Ключевые слова: рапсовый жом, кислота, состав, жирная кислота, полиненасыщенные жирные кислоты, мононенасыщенные жирные кислоты, биологическая ценность, эруковая кислота, tokoferol, xolin, олеиновая кислота.

Introduction

One of the priority tasks of the state is to provide the population with food products rich in nutritional and biological value. To expand this problem, the planting of various crops is expanding, new varieties are being developed, and non-standard secondary resources are being used so that it does not affect the cost of finished food products. One of the promising ones in

this direction is rapeseed, which produces oil whose nutritional value exceeds that of olive oil. Another valuable product is rapeseed squeeze formed after obtaining oil, but there is practically no data on food safety, physical and chemical composition, nutritional, biological, and energy value of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This determined the direction of our research. We studied the fatty acid composition and content of water and fat-soluble acids in rapeseed squeeze [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The fatty acid composition of oils was determined by gas chromatography on a “Kristall 2000” chromatograph. The oils were prepared for analysis on a chromatograph according to “GOST 30418-96. Vegetable oils. Method for determining fatty acid composition.” Oils in an amount of 100 mg were dissolved in hexane (2 ml), 100 µl of ethylation reagent was added, 1 µl of the resulting solution was injected into the chromatograph with a micro syringe. The composition of fatty acids was determined using a gas chromatograph. The analysis was carried out using a capillary quartz column HP-5 ms 30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 µm (stationary phase: 5% diphenyl, 95% dimethylsiloxane) from Agilent [2].

Programming the column thermostat temperature: isotherm 40 °C for 1 min - heating to 210 °C at a rate of 15 °C/min - heating to 150 °C at a rate of 7 °C/min - heating to 280 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min - isotherm 280 °C 10 min.

- Carrier gas: helium, carrier gas rate: 1 ml/min.
- Evaporator temperature 280 °C.
- Ion source temperature 150 °C.
- Quadruple temperature 230 °C.
- Temperature of the transition chamber is 280 °C.
- Reset 1:10.
- The volume of injected liquid sample is 1 µl.

To identify components, linear retention indices were determined, and the results obtained and the full mass spectrum were compared with library (NIST 2.0 mass spectral libraries) and literature data. Only components identified by the library with a probability greater than 90% were considered. Quantitative analysis was carried out based on the areas of the corresponding peaks in the chromatogram constructed using the total ion current.

Sampling of rapeseed squeeze was carried out in accordance with GOST 13496.0; preparation of samples of rapeseed squeeze was carried out in accordance with GOST 31218. The content of choline chloride in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by the colorimetric method. The essence of the method is the extraction of choline chloride with distilled water, the formation in the presence of trisodium phosphate, rein cat complex, choline chloride and colorimetric measurement of the color intensity of its acetone solutions. The content of (nicotinic acid) in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by the colorimetric method.

The essence of the method is the acid hydrolysis of bound forms of (nicotinic acid), purification of the hydrolyze, obtaining a colored solution and colorimetric determination in comparison with a standard solution.

The content of (nicotinic acid) in the composition of rapeseed squeeze was determined by high-performance liquid chromatography.

The essence of the method is the extraction of (nicotinic acid) from the analyzed sample of rapeseed squeeze with a solution of hydrochloric acid and the subsequent determination of its content using a liquid chromatograph [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the above literature review shows, the nutritional and biological value of rapeseed squeeze has been studied in almost many countries. The amino acid, fatty acid composition, content of minerals and acids were studied. As we wrote earlier, rapeseed is one of the promising types of oilseed crops in Uzbekistan. In the future, rapeseed cultivation will increase. This will help increase the amount of secondary rapeseed raw material generated [4]. In our republic, we also studied the fatty acid composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in Uzbekistan to study the nutritional value. (Table 1).

Table No. 1. Fatty acid composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in Uzbekistan.

Name of indicators, units of measurement	Test results and uncertainty			Research methods [methodology], [regulatory document, methodology for test methods]
	Rapeseed oil [a variety containing less erucic acid].	Rapeseed- 1	Soybean cake	
Methyl hexanoate C 60	Not detected	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl octanoate C 80	Not detected	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl decanoate C10,0	Not detected	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl dodecanoate C12,0	Not detected	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl myristate C 14,0	Not detected - 0.2	0.15	0.4	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl palmitate C 16,0	2.5-7.0	4.28	4.3	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl palmitoleate C16,1	Not detected - 0.6	0.22	0.1	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl heptadecanoate C17,0	Not detected - 0.3	0.1	No data	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl cis-10 heptadecanoate C17,1	Not detected - 0.3	0.16	No data	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl stearate C18,0	0.8-3.0	1.73	1.47	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl cis-9 oleate C18,1	51.0-70.0	62.9	9.0	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl linoleidate and Methyl linoleate C18,2	15.0-30.0	19.6	20.9	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl gamma linolenate C18,3	5.0-14.0	8.3	No data	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl arachidate C20,0	0.2-1.2	0.54	0.3	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl cis-11- eicosenoate C20,1	0.1-4.3	1.38	No data	GOST 31663-2012
Methyl cis-11, 14- eicosenoate C20,2	Not detected - 0.1	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012

Methly behenate C22,0	Not detected - 0.6	0.25	No data	GOST 31663-2012
Methly enicate C22.1	Not detected - 2.0	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012
Methly cis-13,16- docosadienoate C22,2	Not detected - 0.1	Not detected	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012
Methly lignocarate C24,0	Not detected - 0.3	0.09	No data	GOST 31663-2012
Methly nervonate aka methyl cis-15- tetracosanoatr C24,1	Not detected - 0.4	0.08	Not detected	GOST 31663-2012

As can be seen from the data in table 1, the fatty acid content of rapeseed squeeze is sufficient. To compare the content of fatty acids, we chose soybean cake as an analogue. The fatty acid composition of rapeseed squeeze consists of saturated fatty acids - 6.16% (myristic - 0.15%, palmitic - 4.28%, stearic - 1.73%), monounsaturated fatty acids - 62.9%, (oleic -62.9%), polyunsaturated fatty acids - 28.7%, (linolenic- ω -6 - 19.6%), alpha-linolenic ω -3 - 8/3%, eicosadiene -1.3) [5].

As the analysis of the results shows, rapeseed squeeze has a valuable fatty acid composition with a predominance of unsaturated fatty acids, including essential polyunsaturated fatty acids of the ω -3 and ω -6 families (ratio 1:3) which play an important role in regulating fat metabolism, lowering cholesterol levels, thrombosis processes and preventing a number of other diseases, including diseases. Here we especially wanted to highlight the high content of oleic acid of the ω -9 family, 62.9% of the total acids. Which is converted into linolenic and α -linolenic acid, which are not synthesized in the human body, i.e. are indispensable for him and should only be supplied with food. The nutritional value of fatty acids from rapeseed grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan can be found in the above tables. Meristic, palmitic, and stearic acids contained in rapeseed are characterized by bactericidal, virucidal, fungicidal activity, capable of potentiating the antibacterial effect of antibiotics in the intestine, and helps to increase the body's immune response to the introduction of an intestinal pathogen. Here, the properties of palmitic acid are ambiguous and since it is contained in breast milk, it is completely absorbed by the child's body, and palmitic acid from palm oil and cow's milk, on the contrary, binds molecules of fatty acids and Ca^{2+} form insoluble salts, causing constipation and disrupting bone formation. When assessing the quality of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the content of unsaturated fatty acids in their composition is of great importance. In rapeseed squeeze, the most significant are two representatives of the family of polyunsaturated fatty acids - linoleic and linolenic acids. The significance and physiological role of polyunsaturated fatty acids in the human body is largely related to their metabolites. According to researchers, polyunsaturated fatty acids of the omega-3 family normalize fat metabolism, increase vascular plasticity, reduce blood viscosity, and activate the immune system [6]. Deficiency of polyunsaturated fatty acids is one of the main nutritional disorders of modern humans [14]. Polyunsaturated fatty acids linoleic with 18:2 ω -6, linolenic with 18:3 ω -3, eicosenoic with 20:1 are important essential nutritional factors: they are not synthesized in the body and must be supplied with food [7]. By studying the composition of polyunsaturated fatty acids in rapeseed squeeze obtained after squeezing the oil from the seeds, we can conclude that adding them as additives to the recipes of various food products will contribute to their enrichment with

polyunsaturated fatty acids. Oleic acid is known to reduce the risk of heart disease, diabetes, obesity, high blood pressure, they can also improve mood, slow the aging process, and prevent cancer. They are part of the omega-9 class of monounsaturated fatty acids and play an active role in many body processes, studying the composition of cell membranes and the activity of receptors located on this membrane. The same above-mentioned qualities are possessed by menthol, with 18:2 ω -6, and arachidic acid with 20:0, which are contained in rapeseed squeeze. Contained in rapeseed squeeze, eicosenoic acid with 20:2 ω - 6 plays the role of a plant and human metabolite, which belongs to the class of omega-9 monounsaturated fatty acids. Rapeseed squeeze also contains eicosadiene acid (20:2 ω -6), behenic acid (22:0), and erucic acid (C 22:1). Eicosadienoic acids are converted by desaturases in vivo to eicosatrienoic acids, which are potent vasodilators [8]. Here I would like to note the content of erucic acid with 22:1 in rapeseed squeeze. Erucic acid is a monounsaturated acid, but it is toxic in large quantities. It is allowed to be consumed according to GOST 8988-2002 in quantities up to 5%. Currently, rapeseed varieties with low erucic acid content have been created. In our republic, rapeseed varieties are grown: “Elvis”, “Tavrion”, “Viking”, “Ruyan”, which are eruce-free and high-oil bearing. Here are some characteristics of these varieties: Tavrion, Elvis, Winter rapeseed varieties (Brassica napus var. Napus) OO type variety (eruk-free, low-glucosinolate). Early ripening: Ruyan, Viking: varieties of spring rape (Brassika napus var. Napus) OO type variety (non-erucic, low lucosinolate), low olinolic. Since we are studying the fatty acid composition of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan, we decided to compare the composition of rapeseed squeezeobtained in the Republic of Belarus (which was obtained by scientists from the Belarusian University of Food and Chemical Technologies) [9].

Pictue 1. Comparative values of the fatty acid composition of rapeseed squeezegrown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarus.

As a comparative analysis of the results of rapeseed squeezes from Uzbekistan and Belarus shows, the content of oleic acid in rapeseed squeezeis 62.9% compared to 60.4% and 2.5% more. Also high content of stearic acid - 0.15% and 0.10%, heptadeconic acid - 0.16% and 0.10%, arachidic acid - 0.54% and 0.40%, eicosenoic acid - 1.38% and 0.80 %, which confirms

the high amount of fatty acids in rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is not inferior to the fatty acid composition of rapeseed grown in the Republic of Belarus [10].

CONCLUSION: Presented studies of rapeseed squeeze grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan on fatty acid and acid composition. As a result of the study, new data was obtained on the fatty acid and acid composition; rapeseed squeeze contains polyunsaturated and monounsaturated fatty acids of the ω -3 and ω -6 families containing fatty acids that are very valuable and they are not synthesized by the body and must be supplied with food. The content of polyunsaturated fatty acids is linolenic (ω -6%), (ω -19.6%). Alpha linolenic (ω -3%) and (ω -8.3%) high content of monounsaturated fatty acids – oleic acid 62.9% shows the high nutritional value of fatty acids of rapeseed squeeze. When studying the acid composition, a high content of pantothenic acid was determined - 42.5 mg/100g, acid PP 11.9 mg/100g, choline 6.7 mg/100g, acid E 4.4 mg/100g, which indicates the high biological value of rapeseed squeeze, A comparative analysis of rapeseed squeezes grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan and Belarus is also provided, which indicates that it is superior in fatty acid and acid composition to the Belarusian selection. The practical significance of the research data lies in the fact that new data have been obtained on the fatty acid and acid composition of rapeseed squeeze and it will be the basis for the development of additives and fillers from the squeeze to increase the nutritional and biological values of products and national dishes. I would like to note that the introduction as an additive does not affect the cost of these dishes.

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